

The Kinetics of the Decarboxylation of Quinaldonic Acid in Catechol and *o*-Cresol

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Manuscript received 17 January 1977, revised 13 June 1977, accepted 17 June 1977

The decomposition of quinaldonic acid has been studied over the range 140 to 180° in the solvents catechol and *o*-cresol. The formation of a new compound involves the elimination of hydroxyl group with substitution of quinolyl anion in catechol and *o*-cresol. The observed Arrhenius parameters are: $E = 29.57$ Kcals mole⁻¹ and $\log A, \text{sec}^{-1} = 10.49$, in catechol and in *o*-cresol, $E = 33.40$ Kcals mole⁻¹ and $\log A, \text{sec}^{-1} = 12.38$. The normal pre-exponential factor, modest activation energy and tentative evidence of ions to the mechanism are viewed as supporting a bimolecular mechanism via an activated complex, comparison is made with that of picolinic acid in catechol.

IN the past, several kinetic studies have been reported on the decarboxylation of benzoic acid¹, oxalic acid², oxamic acid³, oxanilic acid⁴, malonic acid⁵ and cinnamylidenemalonic acid⁶ in the solvents resorcinol and catechol. The difference existing between picolinic acid⁷ and quinaldonic acid is an additional benzene ring attached to it. It was expected that quinaldonic acid might follow the same mechanism as does picolinic acid in catechol. The picolinic acid decarboxylated in catechol in a manner analogous to malonic acid. Verhock⁸ presented intermediate anion mechanism for the decarboxylation of various acids on the basis of kinetic investigations. However, no direct chemical evidence could be obtained for the occurrence of anions. The rapid reaction of the anions from dibromomalonic acid with bromine was reported by Pederson⁹ and then later Muss¹⁰. Hall¹¹ found that mono-anion and the diacids have different rates of decomposition in aqueous solutions. We have reported in our earlier findings that mono-oxalate ion¹² and the free acid have different rates of decomposition in glycerine medium. The quinaldonic acid has never been the subject of kinetic study in catechol and *o*-cresol, it was found necessary to see whether it follows the same mechanism to that of picolinic acid or not. Kinetic evidence is presented for an ionic mechanism for the decarboxylation of quinaldonic acid in these solvents.

Experimental

Quinaldonic acid used in this investigation was prepared by the bromination of quinaldine in glacial acetic acid in the presence of sodium acetate, 2-tribromomethyl quinaldine was obtained and hydrolysis of the latter by boiling with dilute sulphuric acid yielded quinaldonic acid. Recrystallised the quinaldonic acid several times with glacial acetic acid. It melted at 156.3°, the reported *m.p.* in the literature is 157°.

Catechol and *o*-cresol (BDH) analar grade, *m.p.* = 105° and *b.p.* = 191° respectively.

The kinetic experiments were conducted in a constant temperature oil-bath $\pm 0.05^\circ$ as described in our previous articles^{14,15}. In each set of experiments 0.3088 g sample of quinaldonic acid (the amount which was just required to produce 40.0 ml of CO₂ at NTP) was dropped in the usual manner into the reactor, containing 50 g catechol and 50 g catechol and 50 g *o*-cresol in separate runs.

Results

The decarboxylation was studied in catechol and *o*-cresol at the same temperatures for comparison of the results (Table 1). The plots of $\log(V_\infty - V_t)$ vs t were linear in all the experiments indicating first order, where V_∞ is the maximum volume of CO₂ at the completion of the reaction and V_t is the volume at any time t . The average rate constants obtained from the slopes of the logarithmic plots are shown in Table 1. The plot of $\log k$ against reciprocal of the absolute temperature for each solvent resulted in straight lines. Energy of activation was calculated as $E = 2.303 \times R \times \text{slope}$. The thermodynamic parameters were calculated using Eyring equation based upon the data are tabulated in Table 3 along with the data of picolinic acid. Table 2

TABLE 1.—RATE-CONSTANTS FOR DECOMPOSITION OF QUINALDINIC ACID IN CATECHOL AND *o*-CRESOL.

Run temp. °C	No. of data pairs	Av. $k_1 \times 10^6$ (sec ⁻¹)	No. of data pairs	Av. $k_1 \times 10^6$ (sec ⁻¹)
		Catechol		<i>o</i> -Cresol
150	3	1.413	2	1.48
160	3	3.162	3	3.20
170	2	6.607	2	8.71
180	2	14.130	2	20.89

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF WATER ON THE RATE-CONSTANTS OF THE REACTION AT 180°C.

H ₂ O added	1 ml	2 ml	3 ml	4 ml
Catechol ($k_1 \times 10^5$) sec ⁻¹	13.0	12.4	11.0	9.4
<i>o</i> -Cresol ($k_1 \times 10^5$) sec ⁻¹	19.3	18.0	16.1	13.3

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

	E kcal/ mole	log A (sec ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger kcal/ mole	ΔF^\ddagger kcal/ mole	ΔS^\ddagger cals/ mole/deg.
Catechol	29.57	10.49	28.69	34.67	-13.59
<i>o</i> -Cresol	33.40	12.38	32.52	34.52	- 4.61
Catechol [†] (Picolinic acid)	35.40	13.50	34.56	34.34	+ 2.50

shows the decrease of rate constants by the addition of small amounts of water in the reactor with the solvents, when the reactor attained a constant required temperature, the acid was dropped. Water affected the rates quite considerably.

Discussion

The decarboxylation of quinaldinic acid is kinetically first order similar to picolinic acid. The rate-determining step is an intermediate complex between the acid and the solvents analogous to several carboxylic acids^{16,17}. The reaction mechanism may be presented in the following form :

The reaction (1) is slow and rate-determining step, the transition complex, yielded (the products) hydrogen ion, quinolyl anion and carbon dioxide. However in the second step the quinolyl anion and the solvent might be combining to form phenyl quinoline displacing OH⁻ from the adjacent position in catechol. Hence the rapid addition/substitution might be taking place. The displaced OH⁻ ion forms water combining with H⁺, from the reaction (1). The rapid reactions of step (2) and (3) might be affecting the velocity of a reaction for the decomposition of the acid. For comparison, a similar solvent in which methyl and hydroxyl groups are adjacent was selected to study the reaction mechanism. In *o*-cresol, rates are relatively faster than that of catechol, possibly the isolated methyl group of the solvent having more accelerative effect than that of the isolated hydroxyl group of catechol^{16,19}. However, the relatively low activation energy for a reaction is related to the effective negative charge on the solute causing an increase in the attraction between the solvent and quinolyl anion. The H⁺ and OH⁻ ions are also partly responsible in lowering the energy of activation in comparison to picolinic acid. Hence higher rates and higher energy of activation for picolinic acid in catechol. Apart from this, the intermediate complex of picolinic acid in the solvent catechol is smaller in size than that of quinaldinic acid in catechol. Hence bulkier the complex, slower the rate and more stable the complex and more negative the entropy of activation. Picolinic acid gave positive entropy of activation whereas quinaldinic acid showed negative entropy of activation (Table 3). The lowering of ΔS^\ddagger is undoubtedly attributable to the fact that extensive association is obtained between solvent and quinolyl anion and H⁺ ions and undissociated molecules of catechol.

Picolinic acid is a stronger acid than quinaldinic acid. One would predict, therefore that ΔH^\ddagger would be larger for picolinic acid. The high steric factor and high value of enthalpy of activation are in accordance

Structure 1

without predictions for picolinic acid. Hence, there would be less steric hindrance in the formation of activated complex. The added water of the reaction showed that the reaction velocity is retarded in both the solvents of this investigation (Table 2). This indicates that the decarboxylation reaction is suppressed by the addition of water. The water molecule probably adds across the carbonyl double bond of the activated complex and stabilizes the complex. The reaction mechanism in catechol and *o*-cresol is similar and is shown above.

In this reaction the end products are methyl-phenyl quinoline and water and in reaction (1) phenyl quinoline and water. It was expected that H^+ ions might be accelerating the rates but the fast reaction of ($H^+ + OH^-$) could not effect on the rate. However this is beyond expectation.

The first order kinetics and the simplicity of the stoichiometry between 150–180° interpretation of the findings is thus limited. We believe the results at hand lead mild support to the assumption of ionic decomposition mechanism through the formation of activated complex. The direct hydrogen transfer to carbon in the benzene ring occurs due to the formation of C–C bond between solvents and quinolyl anion but the entropy of activation would seem to be somewhat high for the formation of three benzene rings. The formation of methylphenyl quinoline, phenylquinoline involve the elimination of hydroxyl group with substitution by quinolyl anion in the adjacent position. Similar displacements in an adjacent position have been studied by Gilman and coworkers²⁰ who however reported no mechanism.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. H. Siddiqui and C. Balasubramaniam for illuminating discussion. We also extend our thanks to Khalid Sayyed for his careful reading of this manuscript.

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